

TOPICALITY OF INVESTIGATING PSYCHOLOGICAL TERMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT

The article illustrates how much research has been carried out in the field of psychological terminology. Also it emphasizes the essence of its investigation. Particularly, comparative analysis of English and Uzbek terms can serve as an enrichment of the domain of terminology.

The events taking place in public life are most clearly reflected in the vocabulary of the language. The changing reality, requiring new names, activates, in turn, the individual links of the lexical system of the language. Scientific achievements of the late 20th early 21st centuries left an imprint, first of all, on the terminology, as the most intensively developing layer of the lexical composition of the language, which has been significantly influenced by extra linguistic factors. In recent decades, special terminological systems began to appear that combine the words of a particular field of knowledge, and in the 80s of the twentieth century, a new independent field of knowledge appeared - terminology is a complex scientific discipline that studies special vocabulary.

The scope of use of any terms is limited by the scope of the science they are discussing. This allows terminological units to function in their highly specialized terminological system, while revealing all their structural, semantic and functional features. [4;3]

Investigating terms is ever-lasting process. In the global linguistics, in particular, in the science of comparative linguistics the need for research of terms in technology, social-humanitarian and political spheres is growing. The importance of learning terms is topical in the status quo too and there are two main mediums through which terms are studied:

1. The study of terms based on dictionaries.
2. The study of terms based on texts. [2;5]

Regarding psychology, the case is again true as new concepts are emerging in this field. Owing to emerging those new concepts, new terms are needed to express them. Particularly, in order compare English and Uzbek terms efficiently, it should be thoroughly studied. By a thorough study, we mean identifying lexical items' relationship such as synonyms, antonyms, hyponyms, graduonyms, homonyms and paronyms as well as compiling a dictionary regarding psychological terms. These deeds are of vital importance in investigation of psychological terms.[3;5]

Psychological terminology, which forms the basis of the language of science and plays a leading role in the process of general cognition, has not yet received a systematic linguistic description that would reveal the features of the lexical-conceptual structure, development, education, and functioning of the terms of these sciences. The study of the sublanguage of psychology is of considerable interest both in terms of the development of psychological terminology in connection with the evolution of the language system and the history of society, and in terms of the etymological genesis of terms.

As it is commonly known, the term has its own basic properties - only inside the terminological field, outside it, it loses its own definitive and systemic characteristics, and therefore the main features of the terminological field are:

definitivity, monosemy, expressive-stylistic neutrality. [4;9]

Consequently, terminological fields in a broad sense can be recognized as all conceptual fields. But in order to differentiate the scientific picture of the world from the actual linguistic picture of the world, scientists propose to fix the use of the term terminological field only by relation to scientific systems of concepts. The distribution of terms according to the thematic, more precisely, the conceptual-thematic principle provides an opportunity to systematize words-terms according to semantic similarity, to see the specifics of individual groups and subgroups of terms included in: common terminology, reveal their similarities and differences.

A special attention is being paid to the development of systematic relationships in the lexicon of the studied languages in cross-analysis of psychological terms in world linguistics, carrying out cross-linguistic comparative-comparison, their classification, their descriptive research, creating printed and electronic dictionaries of psychology terms, identifying similar and different features of those terms and also their differences in lexical-semantic relations. Also, psychology terms are connected with the mentality, religion, and customs of the members of society, revealing that the internal lexical stock of terminology is enriched due to external lexical influence. These reasons explain the need to study the psychology terminology of English and Uzbek languages in a comparative aspect. [3;5]

Since psychological terminology is not specifically researched in Uzbekistan, the analysis of psychological terms serves to expand the scope of the Uzbek language. With the development of innovative ideas, the terminology of new fields is also developing. Accordingly, based on the principles of development, "first of all, expanding the range of use of our mother tongue, in-depth study of its historical roots and comprehensive development on a scientific basis is becoming a very urgent issue today." [1; 1]

All things considered, terminology is a domain which is always in the spotlight. Especially, it is necessary to study psychological terms and lexical items. Their comparative research may assist in developing systematic and classified lexical items regarding psychology in the Uzbek language.

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